

Supplemental Materials to "Tensor representation of four-magnon interactions Hamiltonian and magnon decay rates suppression by magnetic dipolar interactions in antiferromagnetic insulator NiO"

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I. APPLICATION OF TENSOR REPRESENTATION ON SPONTANEOUS DECAY OF CHIRAL MAGNONS IN TOPOLOGICAL MAGNONICS

Magnetism and magnonic properties of a two-dimensional (2D) collinear ferromagnetic insulator with honeycomb structure, such as CrI₃, have recently been investigated to host rich magnetic interactions, e.g., Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interactions (DMIs) and Kitaev interactions [1–5], without inducing a non-collinear magnetic ground state due to the smaller magnitude of these magnetic interactions than that of isotropic spin-exchange interactions. Furthermore, the DMIs and Kitaev interactions in a collinear magnetic order break the SO(2) symmetry, which is not entirely captured by the second-order magnon Hamiltonian, $\hat{H}^{(2)}$. Particularly, only the DMI component parallel to the magnetic easy axis enters the $\hat{H}^{(2)}$ as the non-spin-conserving term, while the DMI component perpendicular to the magnetic easy axis enters the third-order magnon Hamiltonian, $\hat{H}^{(3)}$, giving rise to magnon decay and renormalization

[6].

In the collinear honeycomb ferromagnet, three-fold rotational and mirror symmetry protect the degeneracy at Dirac crossing, while the second-nearest neighbor DMIs break the time-reversal symmetry and lift the degeneracy at the Dirac crossing, which allows chiral/unidirectional magnon edge states to propagate and leads to a non-trivial topological magnon phase. The inclusion of the third-order magnon Hamiltonian, $\hat{H}^{(3)}$, principally renormalizes and dampens the chiral magnon edge states at zero temperature, where no magnons are thermally excited [7, 8]. In this supplemental material, we applied the tensor representation of multi-magnon interactions to demonstrate the spontaneous magnon decay of chiral edge states of a collinear ferromagnetic honeycomb structure, taking CrI₃ as an example.

A. Tensor Representation of Three-Magnon Interactions

Third-order magnon Hamiltonian, $\hat{H}^{(3)}$, is derived similarly as in the $\hat{H}^{(4)}$ case in the main text, which is given as,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}^{(3)} = & \sum_{\tau, \tau'} \sum_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q} \in BZ}^{N_{at}} -\sqrt{\frac{S_{(\tau)}}{2}} \left(\mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q}}^{(\tau)(\tau', \tau')} \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{q}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau')\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{k}} + \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}', \bar{\tau}')} \hat{a}_{(\tau)-\mathbf{q}} \hat{a}_{(\tau')-\mathbf{p}} \hat{a}_{(\tau)-\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \right) \\ & -\sqrt{\frac{S_{(\tau')}}{2}} \left(\left[\mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{p}}^{(\tau)(\tau', \tau)} \right]^T \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{q}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau')\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{(\tau)\mathbf{k}} + \left[\mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}', \bar{\tau})} \right]^T \hat{a}_{(\tau)-\mathbf{q}} \hat{a}_{(\tau')-\mathbf{p}} \hat{a}_{(\tau)-\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \right), \end{aligned} \quad (S1)$$

where $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{k} - \mathbf{q}$ is the momentum conservation condition from the Fourier transformation, $\bar{\tau} = \tau + N_{at}$, and the $\mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(\tau)(\tau, \tau')}$ and $\mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}, \bar{\tau}')}$ are given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(\tau)(\tau, \tau')} &= \mathbf{u}_{(\tau)}^\dagger J_{\tau\tau'}(\mathbf{k}) \mathbf{v}_{(\tau')}, \\ \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}, \bar{\tau}')} &= \mathbf{u}_{(\tau)}^T J_{\tau\tau'}(\mathbf{k}) \mathbf{v}_{(\tau')}, \end{aligned} \quad (S2)$$

and the element of $J_{\tau\tau'}(\mathbf{k})$ is given by Eq. (8) in the main text.

For a given set of $\{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q}\}$, all the terms in the third-order magnonic field operators can be represented by a

third-rank tensor, which is given by,

$$\hat{H}^{(3)} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q} \in BZ} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{q}}^\dagger \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}}^{(\tau)} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}}^{(N_{at})} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}} \\ \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}}^{(\bar{\tau})} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}}^{(2N_{at})} \mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (S3)$$

where $\mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}}^{(\tau)}$ and $\mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{k}}^{(\bar{\tau})}$ are $2N_{at} \times 2N_{at}$ matrices whose

elements are given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}}^{(\tau)(\tau',\tau'')} &= \delta_{\tau'\tau''} \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q}}^{(\tau)(\tau',\tau')} + \delta_{\tau\tau''} \left[\mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{p}}^{(\tau)(\tau',\tau)} \right]^T, \\ \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}',\bar{\tau}'')} &= \delta_{\tau'\tau''} \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}',\bar{\tau}')} + \delta_{\tau\tau''} \left[\mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{\tau})(\bar{\tau}',\bar{\tau})} \right]^T. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S4})$$

Using the transformation matrix $\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}}$, that is obtained from the diagonalization of the $\hat{H}^{(2)}$, the third-rank tensor in Eq. (S3) is transformed from the basis of $\mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}}$ to the basis of $\Psi_{\mathbf{k}}$, as given by,

$$\hat{H}^{(3)} = \sum_{\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q} \in BZ} \Psi_{\mathbf{q}}^\dagger \begin{pmatrix} \Psi_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}}^{(m)} \Psi_{\mathbf{k}} \\ \vdots \\ \Psi_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}}^{(2N_m)} \Psi_{\mathbf{k}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{S5})$$

where the matrix element of $\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p}}^{(m)}$ is expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}}^{(m)(m',m'')} &= \sum_{\tau=1}^{\bar{N}_{at}} \sum_{\tau'=1}^{\bar{N}_{at}} \sum_{\tau''=1}^{\bar{N}_{at}} \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{q}}^{(\tau,m)} * \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{p}}^{(\tau',m')} * \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbf{k}}^{(\tau'',m'')} \\ &\quad \times \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}}^{(\tau)(\tau',\tau'')} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S6})$$

$\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}}^{(m)(m',m'')}$ represents a three-magnon interaction vertex of a particular process, and all possible three-magnon interactions are shown in Fig. S1. In total, there are four distinct processes of three-magnon interactions. In the first interaction, one magnon is split into two magnons, which is shown diagrammatically in Fig. S1(a). The second interaction corresponds to the reverse process of the first interaction, in which two magnons recombine into one magnon, and is shown diagrammatically in Fig. S1(b). The third interaction corresponds to a simultaneous creation of three magnons from a vacuum state and is shown diagrammatically in Fig. S1(c). The fourth interaction corresponds to a simultaneous annihilation of three magnons into the vacuum state and is shown diagrammatically in Fig. S1(d), and this interaction is the reverse process of the third interaction. Note that during all these interactions, the total momentum of created and annihilated magnons is conserved.

B. Spontaneous Magnon Decay Rates

In this section, we treat the $\hat{H}^{(3)}$ as a perturbation to the $\hat{H}^{(2)}$, and apply the many-body Green's function [9] to obtain the lowest order self-energies. The lowest order of self-energies that gives rise to magnon decay is given by treating the $\hat{H}^{(3)}$ as a second-order perturbation. Previous work in the honeycomb Kitaev model [7] demonstrated that two different magnon decay processes lead to the magnon decay at finite temperature, but only one process leads to the spontaneous magnon decay at zero temperature. The diagrammatic expression of the latter process is given in Fig. S1(e), where

FIG. S1. (Color online) Feynman diagrams of three-magnon interactions for (a) magnons-splitting, (b) magnons-combining, (c) spontaneous creation of three magnons, and (d) spontaneous annihilation of three magnons. (e) Diagrammatic time-domain Green's function of three-magnon interactions that gives rise to Eq. (S7). The color of the circles and lines represents the magnon modes.

the process includes one magnon decaying into two intermediate magnon states. The second-order self-energy of this process is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(2)}(i\omega) &= \sum_{\mathbf{q} \in BZ} \sum_{n,l}^{N_m} \frac{|\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p}}^{(m,n,l)}|^2}{i\omega - \omega_{(n)\mathbf{q}} - \omega_{(l)\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{q}}} \\ &\quad \times (1 + f_{(n)\mathbf{q}} + f_{(l)\mathbf{k}-\mathbf{q}}), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S7})$$

where the $f_{(m)\mathbf{k}} = (\exp(\hbar\omega_{(m)\mathbf{k}}/k_B T) - 1)^{-1}$ is the thermal probability occupation function of magnon mode m under temperature T , and the interaction vertex, $\mathbb{C}_{(m,n,l)\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q}}$, is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p}}^{(m,l,n)}|^2 &= \left| \tilde{\mathbb{C}}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q},\mathbf{p}}^{(m \rightarrow n,l)} + \left(\tilde{\mathbb{C}}_{-\mathbf{k} \rightarrow -\mathbf{q},-\mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{m} \rightarrow \bar{n},\bar{l})} \right)^* \right|^2, \\ \tilde{\mathbb{C}}_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \mathbf{q},\mathbf{p}}^{(m \rightarrow n,l)} &= \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{q},\mathbf{p},\mathbf{k}}^{(n)(l,m)} + \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{p},\mathbf{q},\mathbf{k}}^{(l)(n,m)} + \mathbb{C}_{-\mathbf{k},\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{q}}^{(\bar{m})(l,\bar{n})} \\ &\quad + \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{p},-\mathbf{k},-\mathbf{q}}^{(l)(\bar{m},\bar{n})} + \mathbb{C}_{-\mathbf{k},\mathbf{q},-\mathbf{p}}^{(\bar{m})(n,\bar{l})} + \mathbb{C}_{\mathbf{q},-\mathbf{k},-\mathbf{p}}^{(n)(\bar{m},\bar{l})}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S8})$$

in which the interaction vertex consists of the combination of different tensor elements in Eq. (S6) at different sets of $\{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}\}$. As one can see from Eq. (S7), at $T = 0$ K, in which no magnons are thermally excited, the self-energy of the process given by Fig. S1(e) is non-zero,

FIG. S2. (Color online) (a) A $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ unit cell of CrI_3 as seen from top (upper) and side (lower) view. The blue and purple spheres represent the Cr and I atoms, respectively. (b) A 1D nanoribbon, made on the honeycomb CrI_3 , with 40 Cr atoms width and zig-zag termination. White and black small circles represent two Cr atoms in the 2D unit cell. Blue and red spheres represent the Cr atoms at the two opposite edges, while the green spheres represent the Cr atoms at the middle of the nanoribbon.

which gives rise to spontaneous magnon decay. Using the on-shell approximation [10], the magnon decay rate, $\gamma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}$, is obtained by performing analytic continuation and taking the imaginary part of $\Sigma_{(m)\mathbf{k}}^{(2)}$.

II. GENERALIZED SPIN-EXCHANGE INTERACTIONS OF CrI_3

A. First-Principles Calculation

The electronic structure calculations, based on full-potential linearized augmented plane wave (FLAPW) framework [11], were performed on a $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ CrI_3 2D unit cell to extract the generalized spin-exchange interactions, $J_{\tau\tau'}^{(\mu,\nu)}$, as shown by Fig. S2(a). For exchange-correlation to treat strongly-correlated electrons in Cr

FIG. S3. (Color online) (a) The symmetric part of generalized spin-exchange interactions, $J_{ij}^{(\alpha,\alpha)}$, $J_{ij}^{(\beta,\beta)}$, and $J_{ij}^{(\gamma,\gamma)}$, as functions of spin-pair distance, r_{ij} . The red circles, green squares, and blue triangles correspond to the $J_{ij}^{(\alpha,\alpha)}$, $J_{ij}^{(\beta,\beta)}$, and $J_{ij}^{(\gamma,\gamma)}$, respectively. (b) The anti-symmetric part of generalized spin-exchange interactions, grouped into those parallel to the magnetic easy axis, D_{ij}^{\parallel} , and those perpendicular to the magnetic easy axis, D_{ij}^{\perp} , based on Eq. (S10). The red circles and blue triangles correspond to the D_{ij}^{\parallel} and D_{ij}^{\perp} , respectively. The first- and second-nearest neighbor magnetic interactions are denoted by the subscripts '(1)' and '(2)', respectively [21].

d orbitals and van der Waals interactions, the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) with Hubbard U ($U_{\text{eff}} = 3.0$ eV) [12, 13] and DFT-D2 correction were applied. The plane-wave basis function was expanded in reciprocal space under plane-wave cut-off $|\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}| \leq 7.37 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$. Muffin tin sphere radii of Cr and I atoms were taken to be 1.16 and 1.27 Å, respectively. From geometry optimization, the lattice constant was obtained as 7.04 Å. The $15 \times 15 \times 1$ \mathbf{k} -point mesh was used for Brillouin zone (BZ) sampling that ensures the convergence of the spin-exchange constants.

The generalized spin-exchange constants were obtained via the magnetic force theorem and the linear response approach [14–16] on the 2D unit cell. Then, we mapped the generalized spin-exchange interactions from the 2D unit cell into the 1D nanoribbon unit cell, consisting of 40 Cr atoms, with zig-zag termination (Fig. S2(b)), to capture the magnon edge states decay rates.

B. Magnetic Interactions in Monolayer CrI_3

The generalized spin-exchange tensors, $\mathbf{J}_{0(\tau),\mathbf{R}_1'(\tau')}$, are divided into two parts: symmetric and anti-symmetric parts. The symmetric part of $\mathbf{J}_{0(\tau),\mathbf{R}_1'(\tau')}$ for each spin-pair is diagonalized, resulting in only three elements of

TABLE S1. First-nearest neighbors isotropic spin-exchange constants, $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$, and magnetic anisotropy energy from symmetric spin-exchange interactions, ΔE , of monolayer CrI₃ obtained in the present work, previous first-principles works based on projector augmented wave (PAW) under local density approximation (LDA) [17] with a Hubbard correction U and experiment of Raman spectroscopy [18] (in the unit of meV).

	$J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$	ΔE
This work	-2.32	1.35
Theory		
(PAW+LDA ($U = 0.5$ eV)) [17]	-2.46	1.11
Experiment		
(Raman spectroscopy) [18]	-2.73	

spin-exchange tensors defined in a spin-pair-specific local coordinate system [17]. On the other hand, the DMIs are still defined in the global coordinate system $\{x, y, z\}$. The spin Hamiltonian is expressed as the sum of the diagonalized symmetric and the anti-symmetric (DMIs) parts, as given by,

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{\nu}^{N_{\text{uc}}} \sum_{\mu'=\alpha,\beta,\gamma} J_{0(\tau),\mathbf{R}_{\nu'}(\tau')}^{\mu',\mu'} S_{(\tau)}^{\mu'} S_{(\tau')}^{\mu'} + \mathbf{D}_{0(\tau),\mathbf{R}_{\nu'}(\tau')} \cdot (\mathbf{S}_{(\tau)} \times \mathbf{S}_{(\tau')}). \quad (\text{S9})$$

For the sake of simplicity, the site notation in the symmetric and anti-symmetric parts is changed into $J_{ij}^{\mu',\mu'}$ and $\mathbf{D}_{ij} = (D_{ij}^x, D_{ij}^y, D_{ij}^z)$, respectively.

The $J_{ij}^{(\alpha,\alpha)}$, $J_{ij}^{(\beta,\beta)}$, and $J_{ij}^{(\gamma,\gamma)}$, as functions of spin-pair distances, are given in Fig. S3(a). By calculating the average between these three symmetric spin-exchange interactions in the first-nearest neighbor, the first-nearest neighbor isotropic spin-exchange interactions, $J_{(1)}^{\text{ex}}$, are obtained and compared to previous works in the Table S1, which shows good agreement between them. Furthermore, the total magnetic anisotropy, defined as the total static spin energy difference between magnetization along the \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{z} direction [see Fig. S2(a)], is found to be 1.35 meV, in good agreement with the previous work.

The anti-symmetric parts, \mathbf{D}_{ij} , are further grouped into those parallel to the magnetic easy axis, D_{ij}^{\parallel} , and those perpendicular to the magnetic easy axis, D_{ij}^{\perp} , defined as

$$D_{ij}^{\parallel} = |D_{ij}^z|, \quad D_{ij}^{\perp} = \sqrt{(D_{ij}^x)^2 + (D_{ij}^y)^2}. \quad (\text{S10})$$

The D_{ij}^{\parallel} and D_{ij}^{\perp} , as functions of spin-pair distances, are given in Fig. S3(b). Only the second-nearest neighbor DMIs are effectively non-zero, while other n -th nearest neighbor are smaller than 0.01 meV. The total magnitude of second-nearest neighbor DMIs are around 0.09 meV, which is quantitatively in the same order of magnitude with those in the previous work (0.06 meV in Ref. [19]).

FIG. S4. (Color online) (a) Magnon dispersion of CrI₃ in 1D nanoribbon geometry with zig-zag termination. The red, green, and blue lines correspond to the projected magnon dispersion into red, green, and blue Cr atoms indicated in Fig. S2(b), in which red and blue Cr atoms are located at the two opposite edges of the nanoribbon. (b) Two-magnon states continuum, $D^{(2)}(\mathbf{k}, \omega)$, superimposed with the magnon dispersion. Two red solid bands correspond to the two chiral magnon edge states, and the lower frequency band is denoted as mode-(1). (c) Magnon decay rates of mode-(1), $\gamma_{(1)\mathbf{k}}$. In (b) and (c), two vertical red dotted lines indicate the wave-vector k^* and $-k^*$, where the peak of the two-magnon states continuum and mode-(1) cross [21].

III. MAGNON DECAY RATES OF CHIRAL MAGNON EDGE STATES

By mapping the obtained J_{ij} from the 2D film geometry into the 1D nanoribbon geometry, the magnon dispersion of the 1D nanoribbon is plotted in Fig. S4(a), which is resolved into three Cr atoms contribution located at three different positions in the nanoribbon unit cell in Fig. S2(b). Blue, green, and red lines in the magnon dispersion in Fig. S4(a) correspond to the contribution of Cr atoms indicated by blue, green, and red spheres in Fig. S2(b), respectively. Magnon states between 4.0 and 4.5 THz consists of contribution from two Cr atoms at the opposite edges of the nanoribbon, which indicates the existence of localized magnon edge states.

Furthermore, the chirality of these localized magnon edge states is clearly seen, where each of the localized magnon edge states only allows unidirectional magnon propagation. The profile of the magnon dispersion of the present work gives a good agreement to that of previous work with parameterized spin Hamiltonian [8, 20], where the chiral magnon edge states in the present and previous work are crossing at the Γ .

The two-magnon states continuum, given by Eq. (A2) in the main text, for the 1D nanoribbon magnon dispersion is also plotted in Fig. S4(b) to check the kinematic condition for three-magnon interactions. As one can see, crossings between two-magnon states continuum and the magnon dispersion are observed, which kinematically enable the three-magnon interactions-induced magnon decay to occur. Additionally, we labeled the lower frequency magnon edge states as mode-(1), as illustrated by the lower frequency red solid line in Fig. S4(b). Strong magnon decay of the chiral edge states is expected at the wave-vector k^* and $-k^*$, where the peak of the two-magnon states continuum and the magnon mode-(1) cross.

The magnon decay rates of mode-(1), $\gamma_{(1)\mathbf{k}}$, at $T = 0$ K are shown in Fig. S4(c), where large peaks are observed near the k^* and $-k^*$. As predicted, these large peaks occur due to a lot of magnon decay channels available for three-magnon interactions-induced magnon

decay to occur, which is indicated by the crossing between the peak of the two-magnon states continuum and the magnon mode-(1). In comparison to the previous work [8], the three-magnon interactions in this work only dampen the chiral magnon edge states, which lead to the limited magnon lifetime. Generally, the three-magnon interactions also enable hybridization (i) between magnon edge states and the bulk states and (ii) between two magnon edge states from the opposite edges. The mechanism (i) leads to the delocalization of chiral magnon edge states to the bulk area, while the mechanism (ii) leads to the breaking of topological protection, which allows two counter-propagating magnons at one edge. To take into account both mechanisms, the three-magnon scattering process in Fig. S1(e) has to be generalized to include a process in which the magnon state after the scattering does not return to the initial magnon state before the scattering. Then, the true self-energy is obtained by solving the pole condition of the magnon Green's function, self-consistently [8]. The tensor representation for the three-magnon interaction vertex is then updated for each iteration in the self-consistent calculation, and the tensor representation enables simultaneous calculation of the interaction vertices for a given set of $\{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}\}$, resulting in a faster numerical calculation than manually calculating each combination of magnon states.

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[21] The data that support the findings of this article are openly available in [10.5281/zenodo.17946772](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17946772)